

Building Automation Based on Temporal Planning

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ABSTRACT

Building automation is essential for improving people’s comfort, productivity, and safety, while optimising energy and operational efficiency. We explore the potential of temporal planning as a solution to achieving building automation. We analyse key aspects of building environments, including operations, components, objectives, and other characteristics, to identify their automation requirements. We then propose temporal planning as a promising approach due to its expressive modelling power and its abilities to address complex, constrained problems. We also outline the temporal planning constructs that can effectively represent and manage the diverse challenges inherent in building automation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Building automation is the development and use of technologies, computational techniques and systems to monitor and control a building’s operation. The main objectives of building automation are to increase safety, improve people’s comfort and productivity, increase energy efficiency, and reduce operational costs. Addressing these objectives becomes possible as a result of the cascade of technical innovations at different levels, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), renewables, and advanced computational techniques.

Current building automation systems operate buildings with simple reactive control and feedback mechanisms. While this concept is a step forward, it has many limitations, including unawareness of people’s needs and energy inefficiency as well as a lack of coordinated and anticipated operation. Put differently, actions of devices and systems embedded in buildings should be automatically selected, ordered and executed to maximise occupant needs under the constraints of minimal energy consumption. We call this a *building coordination problem* [6]. Various forms of this problem have been addressed using many techniques, including Artificial Intelligence (AI) planning [7]. AI planning is the process of reasoning about which actions are needed to achieve some objective. We have previously used hierarchical planning to solve a building coordination problem whose objective is a building’s adaptation to people’s activities while consuming as little energy as possible [6]. Although our approach enables proactive building automation that successfully satisfies people’s needs and saves energy by up to 70%, it disregards some important aspects of the building coordination problem, such as its temporal nature and explicit energy concerns.

In this preliminary work, we extend the building coordination problem and explore its modelling as a temporal planning problem. In particular, we analyse building operations, components, and numeric and temporal characteristics of the building coordination problem. We propose to apply temporal planning to solving this problem as it offers the advantage of great expressive power and mechanisms for addressing highly constrained problems. We

explore the application of temporal planning to the building coordination problem by describing how various temporal planning constructs can be used to model the different aspects of the problem.

2 BUILDING COORDINATION PROBLEM

We now describe and categorise, wherever possible, the ingredients of the building coordination problem relevant to our treatment.

2.1 Operations and Components

With the proliferation of the IoT, it becomes possible to not only operate typical building components, such as the heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) system but to extend the monitoring and control to other components, such as appliances and devices, electricity storage systems, and electric vehicles. We organise the building operations in three categories based on what they can be used for. (1) *Ambient operations* maintain healthy, comfortable and productive environment for building occupants. This includes thermal comfort (temperature and humidity), visual comfort (light intensity), air quality (air exchange and CO₂), and acoustic comfort. (2) *Electrical equipment operations* manage appliances and other devices. (3) *Green operations* utilise sustainable energy technology. This includes storage of energy and local energy generation.

The successful building operation depends on various devices and systems embedded in buildings, which we refer to as *components*. These components can be divided into *controllable* and *uncontrollable* components. Controllable components can be directly controlled and are typically endogenous to buildings. These can further be categorised into *background components*, such as water heating, *schedulable components*, such as dishwashers, electric vehicles, and electricity storage, and *combined components*, which can be both scheduled and run in the background, such as space heating and lighting. Uncontrollable components are often exogenous to the building and cannot be controlled. These include uncontrollable demand, renewable energy, and wholesale energy tariffs.

2.2 Numeric and Temporal Characteristics

Several quantities are characteristic for the building operations and components: indoor temperature, humidity, CO₂, light intensity, energy demand, energy cost, energy tariffs, and battery capacity. Many of these quantities are intrinsically linear or non-linear, which means that their computation requires solving *linear functions* or *non-linear functions*. For example, non-linear functions are required to calculate the temperature, CO₂, predicated demand, predicted energy generation, battery charging, and tariff change.

The values these quantities should take are often constrained by various building standards, policies and regulations for maintaining

safe, healthy, and comfortable buildings. We refer to these as *well-being constraints*. Furthermore, there is a set of *temporal constraints*, which can be categorised as *operation constraints*, *ordering constraints*, and *business constraints*. The operation constraints define the start time, earliest start time, latest finish time, and duration of a controllable component's operation. For example, dishwashing may need to occur in a time frame when the energy price is at its lowest. Moreover, the operation constraints may impose deadlines, for example, that require to heat an office well before its occupant comes to the office. The ordering constraints define the dependencies between operations of controllable components, where operations may need to be executed in a specific order (e.g., a window can be opened only after blinds have been pulled up) or concurrently. The business constraints define temporal regulations specific to the business conducted in a building. For example, one business constraint may define the building operating hours.

Another characteristic is that some controllable components may have a flexible operation or operation duration. For example, the duration of operations involving batteries (e.g., charging) can be decided on the fly by the building automation system. The last characteristic indicates that although uncontrollable components cannot be controlled, they provide background information that is temporal. For example, the day-ahead market provides hourly electricity prices. Such information can and should be considered when modelling and solving the building coordination problem.

2.3 Objectives

A building coordination problem may have various and multiple objectives, such as improving comfort, saving energy, and minimising energy cost. The optimisation of energy or cost, however, must not come at the price of risking the safety and comfort of people. In fact, strict total order should be enforced when satisfying these objectives [1]. In any case, the objectives can be accomplished by managing all categories of operations and components. So, we can maximise comfort by regulating the temperature, CO₂, humidity and other environmental factors. We can minimise energy demand by regulating heating, lighting, appliances, and electricity storage. Finally, we can minimise the energy cost by managing the energy demand with respect to the energy tariffs.

3 TEMPORAL PLANNING

Temporal planning is suitable for solving the above building coordination problem as it involves explicit representations of numbers and time in planning problems, allowing modelling problems that require numeric and temporal constraints. The central element of temporal planning are *durative actions*. Durative actions have preconditions, effects, and duration constraints. These can express that actions may need to occur over a time span, preconditions may not need to hold only at the beginning of action execution, effects may need to hold during the entire action execution. Durative actions can have discrete and continuous effects, whereas the latter can have linear or non-linear components. Durative or invariant conditions are required to hold during the action execution. Temporal planning looks for *temporal plans*, which are finite sets of instantaneous actions and tuples of a starting time, durative action, and duration. The total length of the plan duration is called a *makespan*.

Temporal planning introduces the possibility to have concurrency in plans. Concurrency enables finding plans with shorter makespans or achieving some more complex task, such as simultaneous execution of multiple operations. Many real-world problems, including the building coordination problem, have *required concurrency*, that is, they are solvable and only by concurrent plans [3].

4 MODELLING

Our ultimate objective is to model realistic temporal planning domains that support the solution to the building coordination problem. To this end, we explore the temporal planning constructs relevant for modelling the features of the building coordination problem. All of the planning constructs are based on the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) [8]. More specifically, we use the predicate logic of PDDL, durative actions and numeric fluents of PDDL2.1 [5], Timed Initial Literals (TILs) of PDDL2.2 [4], Timed Initial Fluents (TIFs) [9], and external functions of PDDLx [2].

We can use predicate logic to encode domain objects (e.g., heater), and their properties as predicates (e.g., a predicate indicating the heater is turned on). Such predicates can be used to change the state of the respective object (e.g., turn off the heater). Furthermore, we can use durative and instantaneous actions to represent operations of controllable components, depending on whether the operations are schedulable or not. Durative actions have an invariant condition that includes some of the predicates set by the respective TILs.

In addition to predicate logic, we can use functions, which are called numeric fluents. We can use numeric fluents to represent all quantities characteristic for the building coordination problem. We can then use numeric fluents to express well-being and temporal constraints. For example, we can define that the minimum temperature in rooms can reach as low as 20 degC (e.g., (= (min-temp) 20)), and similarly for the maximum temperature. Furthermore, we can use a numeric fluent to encode the total energy cost, which can be maintained with a continuous effect with a non-linear expression.

TILs are constructs that make predicates true or false at some time points. They are particularly useful for specifying deadlines and time frames. Considering the business constraints, we can specify, e.g., the building operating hours 06:00-20:00 as (at 6 (operating-hours)) and (at 20 (operating-hours)). Similar to TILs, TIFs are constructs that change the value of numeric fluents at some time point. For example, we can use TIFs to model the predicted demand as a step function. In general, both TILs and TIFs are useful to model changes that are predicted to occur during the building operation.

PDDLx supports specifying external functions that can be computed with external solvers. This is useful because state-of-the-art temporal planners cannot deal with non-linear functions.

When it comes to the optimising objectives of the building coordination problem, we can use the makespan to minimise the length of its solution. However, it would be more useful to minimise relevant numeric fluents instead. For example, we can minimise the numeric fluent representing the total energy cost, which otherwise increases depending on the selected actions.

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